

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

NEOLOGISMS OF THE RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN WAR PERIOD

Rohalska-Yakubova I.,

Ph.D. in Philology, Associate Professor

State University of Intelligent Technologies and Telecommunications, Odesa, Ukraine

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7975-7801>

Chepelyuk N.

Ph.D. in Pedagogy, Associate Professor

Odesa National Polytechnic University, Odesa, Ukraine

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6822-9691>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12581072>

Abstract

The article is devoted to the analysis of neologisms that appeared in the Ukrainian Internet discourse during the war. In the times of armed confrontations, hate speech begins to be tolerated in the media, negatively coloured innovations are spread to refer to the aggressor country (Bydlostan), its helmsman (Rashenfürher), military (orks). Among neologisms there are lexemes formed according to existing in the language and occasional word-forming types, borrowings, negative synonyms of well-known concepts, semantic neologisms, neographemes that differ only in spelling.

Keywords: neologism, hate speech, borrowings, transformations, semantic neologisms, neographemes, word formation.

1. Introduction

Global socio-political events affect the consciousness of the people, causing changes in behaviour, way of thinking, and worldview. Such fundamental changes in public life as wars, revolutions, and coups change the mental state of society, evoking the strongest emotions possible: from animal fear for life to exaggerated expressions of anger, hatred, and the desire for bloody revenge. However, when it comes to hatred, emotions prevail over rationality (Ortega-Sánchez 2021: 2).

People are inclined to verbalize their feelings and impressions, so in times of war, diary keeping becomes widespread, “hate speech” is tolerated, and an order of magnitude more neologisms appear than would occur through the natural development of language. During the full-scale invasion of Ukraine by Russian troops, the Ukrainian language was enriched with a significant number of neologisms, both neutral or positive, and negative ones as well, that is related to the “hate speech”. People share their emotions, impressions, and feelings on the Internet, where there are no special restrictions or censorship, so pejorative, rude, and swear words are becoming widespread, which, on the one hand, help authors overcome negative emotions, and on the other hand, contribute to the democratization of the language.

The new vocabulary of a certain historical period encodes extensive information about the peculiarities of the economic, political, and cultural life of its era. Moreover, the more important the era is for a particular society, the more saturated it is with vital events, the more actively the language reacts by creating new words (Hrytsenko 2022: 9).

Article structure. The article consists of five sections. The introduction discusses the reasons for the emergence of a large number of new words during the war. The second section describes the purpose and

methodology of the study. The third section is devoted to the analysis of the reasons for the spread of hate speech during military confrontations. The fourth section provides a classification of neologisms recorded in Ukrainian online discourse in 2022-2023. The conclusion summarizes the results of the study of neologisms and the use of hate speech.

2. Aims, material, and methods

The purpose of the article is to study the changes in the language of Ukrainians since the beginning of the war; to trace the connection between emotions and people's speech; the task was to identify author's novelties in the Internet discourse, to analyse the origin, methods of creation, and thematic groups of neologisms of the war period.

Methodology. During the study, we analysed the linguistic reactions of Ukrainians to the outbreak of war in general and to specific military events, and found out what lexical means people use to express their emotions and what neologisms they create. To analyse the neologisms, we used the methods of linguistic text analysis, word-formation analysis of new words, the historical method in terms of studying the origin of key lexemes, and partially the semantic analysis and comparative method of language research.

The source of data is the Internet discourse: news and comments to them as “social media has a great influence on the formation of new words” (Hadžiahmetović & Rahmanović 2020). The analysis focus on the reaction of contributors to a particular military event and the lexical features of the messages. Neologisms in the amount of about 250 units were identified through a continuous sampling from the Internet discourse.

3. The use of hate speech in time of war

The concept of “hate speech”, which means “language of hatred”, appeared in the 1950s, although the

phenomenon dates back to ancient times. One of the components of the primary ontological conceptions of the world was the opposition “friend or foe”. The formation of national identity was based on the identification of differences between those who belong to a certain community of people and those who do not (Kovaleva 2009: 85). This categorization of the world is one of the archetypes of the national subconscious that were identified by C. G. Jung. In the archaic picture of the world, the very existence of the “stranger” was perceived as a threat to the “own”, so the logical reaction was distrust, tension, and even hostility and aggression (Kovaleva 2009: 87). Thus, the “stranger” who posed a threat began to be perceived as an enemy.

In today’s civilized world, where tolerance is promoted, the “stranger” is interpreted as “other” and not as an “enemy”; he or she is not a threat, but has differences. European society is striving for this understanding. However, in the event of wars, armed confrontations, and interethnic conflicts, the basic collective subconscious prevails again: the opponent is perceived as an enemy. In such a situation, “depersonalization of the enemy, defining it as a faceless collective being” (Taranenko 2015: 67) becomes effective, “the image of the opponent is deprived of human features and endowed with behaviour that is completely uncharacteristic of a person the idea of moral inferiority, criminality and negative influence” of the enemy is created (Pryshchepa 2017: 102). The opponent is devalued. V. Kotsur and a group of researchers identify three levels of this process:

1. Lowering of status – switching to “you” (singular, 2nd person); use of the neuter gender in relation to people; distortion of names and surnames (*putler, pulyo, putyasha, putidlo, alkoDimon, vid’mediv*); use of names of diseases or intellectual disability (*debiloidy* (English equivalent – *morons*), *schizorascists*); use of distortions, offensive names of the community, often occasionalisms with negative connotations (*ukr, rascist, moscalota, katsap*);

2. Depreciation to the level of an animal or plant – the use of words for animals, insects, plants (*colorad* (Colorado beetle), *ukrop* (dill), *svynosobaky* (pig-dogs), *zviroidiots* (beastoids), *reptiloid, bulbosaurus*; mocking distortion of surnames or names using words for animals or plants;

3. Devaluation to the level of an inanimate object – the use of words for people that refer to objects (*vata* (cotton wool), *chucheloid* (stuffed animal)); distortion of names, surnames, formation of new words by combining fragments of the surname and words denoting something inanimate (*pukin, pis’kov*); use of words denoting feces, genitals, swear words or dead animals (*stcar, russisia, parashistan*) (Kotsur et al. 2021).

Devaluation, dehumanization, and depersonalization of the enemy lead to the fact that “the physical destruction of the enemy is perceived as more legitimate” (Taranenko 2015: 67), and does not raise moral doubts. There is a theory of social identity based on the idea that social groups improve their cohesion by denigrating other social groups (Bauman et al. 2020).

The question of the benefits of hate speech in wartime remains open, while all researchers of this phenomenon unanimously state that such an attitude is unacceptable in peacetime. O. Horchynska insists that “any case of hate speech is harmful, and each of them must be combated” (Horchynska). D. Yarovyι cautiously states that “for an interstate conflict, the dehumanization of an external enemy does not pose significant dangers” (Yarovyι 2019: 48), while leaving open the question of the positive impact of hate speech on mobilizing society. O. Kokovikhina hypothesises that “hate speech can be useful for non-violent channelling of mental tension” (Kokovikhina 2022: 15) in society towards an external enemy, but warns that its use in the general media should be balanced. V. Kotsur sees positive consequences of using the language of conflict in promoting “psychological discharge at the individual level and reducing socio-psychological tension at the collective level” (Kotsur et al. 2021). In addition, O. Taranenko warns that depersonalization and dehumanization of the enemy are semantic processes of double danger, as they pose a threat not only to the object but also to the subject of the offensive statement (Taranenko 2015: 69).

With the outbreak of hostilities, psycho-emotional tension in society increases, and extraordinary irritating events cause stress. It is possible to understand the inner world of an individual through verbal reactions, so “the analysis of speech during emotional stress is a direct and objective measure that highlights important processes in the psyche and mental health of a person” (Zasiekina et al. 2021) and society as a whole. Of course, language reactions will not be exactly the same for different individuals, and even more so for representatives of different nations, since the choice (even at the subconscious level) is influenced by factors such as psycho-emotional state, stress resistance, upbringing, language preferences, communication competencies, criticality of the situation for the individual, environmental influence, etc. However, negatively coloured metaphors for the enemy appear during any armed conflict (Isakova 2016: 94).

The reason for the spread of rude, abusive words against the enemy is the individual’s internal subconscious desire to get rid of negative feelings, pain, because it is believed that swearing can help harmonise the mental state (Bahan et al. 2022). Furthermore, “by humiliating the opponent, we rise above him/her, he/she shrinks in size, becomes weak, and we feel power and strength” (Karpiak). Irony is a rather relevant and effective “mechanism of psychological self-regulation. It makes it possible to rise above the situation, to look at it from a different perspective. Irony turns what is unbearable, hostile, disturbing for a person into the opposite” (Bahan et al. 2022). That is why during the Russian-Ukrainian war, a significant number of negative names for the enemy appeared, as well as memes that ridicule the typical features and behaviour of opponents.

Initially, negative nominations of the enemy arise in oral communication, later in written communication, and then in the media (Isakova 2016: 93). In February 2022, this process occurred very quickly in Ukrainian

society. The Internet became the mouthpiece of the spread of neologisms for the Russian invaders, due to unlimited access, remoteness, anonymity, and the possibility of interactive communication (Isakova 2016: 93; Kokovikhina 2022: 19; Yarovyi 2019: 70; Castano-Pulgarín et al. 2021: 1). Lexemes with negative connotations have appeared not only in the posts of individuals, but also in electronic media, which can already be interpreted as hate speech. Sometimes the Internet is used to legitimise deviant behaviour (Cohen et al. 2018). In their professional activities, journalists should be guided by the current laws, which prohibit the use of “statements that spread, incite, support or justify racial hatred, xenophobia, anti-Semitism and other forms of hatred caused by intolerance, including intolerance manifested in the form of aggressive nationalism and ethnocentrism, discrimination against minorities and hostile attitudes towards them” (Recommendation 97; Recomendación 2016). Any posts that disparage a person are treated as hate speech on the Internet (Zhang & Luo 2018). This also includes derogatory words, vulgarity or sarcasm (Malmqvist 2015), stereotyping of social groups (Papacharissi 2004), demonstration of discriminatory views (Bhavnani et al. 2009), speculation, comparisons, derogatory comments, slander, incitement to riot, threats, name-calling (Lingam & Aripin 2017), any offensive statements aimed at a particular group of people (Watanabe et al. 2018). The first large-scale systematic research on hate speech on social media is presented in the works of Mondal et al. (2018).

Despite the pan-European trend away from hate speech, both Ukrainian and Russian media outlets are constantly publishing harsh statements against the enemy during the war. In this way, the authorities are trying to mobilise the population to fight, to create an image of a dehumanised enemy, which is considered legal in such circumstances. Hate speech performs the functions of “strengthening intragroup cohesion, forming an image of an imaginary enemy, preserving the integrity of the internal group, and channelling mental tension” (Kokovikhina 2022: 15). Some politicians consider hate speech to be a trivial act of accidents or an act of virtue (Ben-David & Matamoros-Fernandez 2016), spreading racist, ethnic, religious and/or gender stereotypes. Sometimes freedom of speech is misinterpreted as the freedom to hate and write about it (Meza et al. 2018). As a result of spreading such views, pessimistic opinions appear that social media platforms are losing the fight against online hate (Johnson et al. 2019).

According to our observations, at the beginning of the full-scale invasion of Ukraine by Russian troops, there was a serious surge in hate speech on the Internet, when people wanted to verbally express their anger, contempt, and aggression, and the media successfully seized this opportunity. This technique helped to unite Ukrainian society in the fight against the external enemy, and all internal misunderstandings and disagreements faded into the background. There was a significant outbreak of patriotism, which helped the defenders achieve significant success. However, the long-term maintenance of hatred and anger among the people can bring negative consequences in the form of riots, coups,

etc. Over time, emotional tension decreases, as the affective state cannot be too long. In 2023, there are fewer swear words and offensive language in online posts.

4. Results and discussion

The war in Ukraine has led to the emergence of a number of new words within a few months. Enriching a language with new words is a natural part of its evolution (Osovska 2023: 19). Most of the words originated in the spoken language and quickly came into use thanks to the Internet. According to Zh. Koloiz, each new word appears as an occasionalism because it has an author and is used in a specific situation (Koloiz 2009: 62), but later, if the author is not significant and is forgotten, and the neologism is understandable outside the context of its origin, it can spread in society and become public domain. Due to their appearance in the spoken word, modern Ukrainian neologisms often have shades of coarseness, vernacular, and even vulgarity.

When researching new vocabulary, scholars usually pay attention to the reasons for its emergence, the way it enters the language, word-formation features, and thematic groups of neologisms. The act of appearance of a new word in the language should be identified with the word-forming act of derivation in the broad sense of the word (Walczak 1992: 232). The emergence of new words in 2022 was stimulated primarily by extra-linguistic factors, namely, opposition to Russian aggression, military assistance from friendly countries, a decrease in the level of censorship and self-censorship, and changes in language tastes and fashion (Styshov 2022: 43). A significant number of names for weapons and military equipment have appeared; these are borrowings from other languages (HIMARS, *javelin*, *bayraktar*, *shahed*), as well as Ukrainian figurative names formed by metaphorisation (*zelenka* – forest belt, *pad-dle* – flamethrower, *piglets* – mortar shells). The decrease in censorship has led to the formation of swear words (*svynorusy* (pig-headed people), *bydlostan* (a country of cattle), *chmonia* (the enemy's soldier), *krem-liad'* (kremlin minions)), which often become tolerated in wartime in relation to the enemy. The intra-linguistic reasons are dominated by the desire to give preference to more expressive language forms (Styshov 2022: 43), and given that these are nominations of the enemy, negatively coloured new words have appeared (*rusofascist*, *fakomet* (fake news producer), *nedoimperia* (under-empire)).

Scholars divide all new words into groups:

1. Actual neologisms characterized by novelty of form and content, including borrowings;
2. New words – words with a new form and meaning, formed from specific morphemes according to productive word-formation models;
3. Transformations – other names of known realities, novelty is inherent only in the form, but not in the content;
4. Semantic neologisms – forms existing in the language that change their meaning in whole or in part by adding a new lexical and semantic variant (Ladonia 2018: 39). Due to the instability of the terminology, in the works of O. Serbenska the first group is called borrowings, and the second – new words, semantic neologisms are called words with redistribution of meanings,

there are no transformations, but there is such a group as revived words and expressions from the past, this group is called reactivation by M.I. Tretiak (Tretiak). A well-known neologism researcher, Professor O. Styshov, provides a similar classification, distinguishing between neologisms, neologisms, transformations, semantic and functional (revived from the past) neologisms (Styshov 2005: 46-52).

V. I. Zabolotkina divides new words into three groups:

1. Neologisms proper;
2. Semantic innovations or rethinking;
3. Renaming or transformation (Dziubina 2018: 38-39).

To summarize, we propose to divide neologisms into the following groups:

1. Neologisms – all new words formed from native and borrowed morphemes according to the existing Ukrainian language and occasional word-formation models;
2. Borrowings – words of foreign language origin written in the original language or by transliteration, which were not involved in derivational processes in the Ukrainian language;
3. Transformations – new names for previously known concepts;
4. Semantic neologisms – new schemes of previously known lexemes, including outdated ones;
5. Reactivators – neologisms that have returned from a group of archaisms or historicisms without changing their meaning;
6. Neographemes – words that differ from existing ones only in their novelty of spelling, but the meaning remains the same.

Some neologisms can simultaneously belong to the group of new words and transformations if they are formed by one of the morphemic methods, but are synonymous with well-known concepts. For example, the word *bydlostan*, formed by basic compounding, is a rough synonym for the lexeme “Russia”. Most of the neologisms-transformations denoting the aggressor country and its president in the Ukrainian Internet discourse of the two years of war are written with a lowercase letter to emphasize contempt (Yarovyi 2019: 110) for the invader.

4.1 Neologisms

Among the neologisms of the period under study, the first group is the most widely represented. We refer to new words formed by morphemic methods. Morphemic methods of word formation include suffixation, prefixation, inflection, postfixation, stemming, abbreviation, truncation, telescoping, and several non-usual methods. Traditionally, most words in the Ukrainian language are formed by adding suffixes. Wartime new words are no exception – about 20%. The following suffixes have become relevant: **-y-** (*ukrainyty* (*ukrainied*), *javelinyty* (*javelined*), *stingeryty*, *kimyty*, *pryt'ulyty*), **-ets'** (*azovets'* (*azovite*), *bydlostanovets'*, *wagnerivets'*), **-ist-** (*rascist*), **-ant-** (*uhyliant* (*evader*)), **-iuk-** (*Jonsoniuk*), suffixoid **-oid-** (*putinoid*), **-ok-** (*putlerok*), **-iash-**, **-ush-** (*putiasha*, *pylusha*), **-k-** (*rashka*),

-sk-/tsk- (*moskalatsky*, *rascistsky*), **-n-** (*rusnya*, *moskalnya*), **-ot(a)** (*moskalota*), **-ism-** (*rascism*, *putlerism*), **-iy-** (*katsapiya*), **-yt-** (*moskovyt*) etc.

The second most frequently used base was the foundation – 19%. Stemming is a word-formation process that involves two or more source words (Grlj 2022: 87; Enesi 2017: 8). The most productive stems are: **-rus-** with the variant **-ros-** and the English-language equivalent **-russ-/rush** etc. (*russofascist*, *russophonia*, *rashostan*, *schizorascism*), the swear words **bydl-** (*bull-*) (*bydlomassa* (*bullmass*), *bydlorus'* (*bullrussia*)) and **swyn-** (*swynorusy* (*pig + Russian*), *swynosobaka* (*pig-dog*)), **ork-** (*ork-population*, *orkostan*), **bulb-** (*bulbosaurus*, *bulboführer*), **bander-** (*banderomobile*, *banderosmuthies*), **moscv-** (*moscvabad*, *moscvoroty*), **-stan** (*bydlostan*, *parashystan*), **-liandii** (**-land-**) (*rushliandiia* (*rushland*)), German **führer-** (*russianführer*). The letter “Z” is used in the creation of words, replacing the word “Russia” (*z-patriot*, *z-fans*, *z-blogger*, *z-occupiers*). Stemming is a productive way to create new words in English-language Internet discourse as well (Hadžiahmetović 2018).

About 5% of words are formed by the prefix method. Prefixes give words additional meanings (Maharramova 2023: 236). The range of prefixes is small: **za-**, **vid-** (**from**), **na-** (*zabayraktaryty*, *zaenloity*, *vidhimarsyty*, *navolonteryty*) indicate a completed action; **un-** (**der-**) (*under-land*, *under-empire*, *under-imperial*) indicates an incomplete manifestation of a feature; **pro-** (*pro-rascist*) indicates a commitment to something.

Different types of abbreviations account for 3% of new words: **TOT** = *temporarily occupied territory*, **ter-oborona** = *territorial oborona (defence)*, **terrussia** = *terrorist russia*, **puhitler** = *Putin + Hitler*. While in English-language Internet discourse, an abbreviation is the most common way of word formation (Blaženović 2024: 38). Sometimes previously formed abbreviations become building blocks for new words as separate morphemes: *ZSUist*, *ZSUistka*, *fsbuk*, *rfia*, *rfiany*, *chmonia*, *chmobik* – suffixation; *alkofsb*, *narcofsb* – base formation. The word “E-grave” was created using the well-known English abbreviation *electronic*, which is visually similar to the Ukrainian verb “to be” in the present tense. In Slavic linguistics, there is still a debate about the status of new words with reduced foreign language elements: whether they should be classified as base formation, splicing, or separated into a separate group of composites (Jadacka 2001: 94, 106; Ochmann 2004: 38–45; Waszakowa 2005: 54–55, 71–72), or may treat such foreign elements as prefixes (Jadacka 1995: 161; Waszakowa 2005: 55).

The inflectional method was used to form 2.5% of neologisms: *zadvokhsotyty*, *vidkobzonyty*, *vidbanderyty* that means to kill, *zatriokhsotyty* – to wound, *zadupie* – a rude name for Russia. The postfixed method accounted for 1% of new words: *haotyzyvatysia* (*chastise*), *zadvokhsotytytsia*. The unaffixed method is used to create the crude name of the country, *rakha*, which is derived from *Russia*, and the consonants *kh/sh* are alternated. The words *mobik* (*mobilized* – truncated to *mob* + *-ik-*), *termukha* (*thermal underwear* – truncated to *term* + *-ukh-*) were formed by truncation followed by suffixation.

Among the non-usual ways of word formation, Zh. Koloiz includes contamination, substitution, reduplication, emancipation of affixes or phonemes, gendiadis, holophrasis, and stepwise word formation (Koloiz 2015: 76-77). These formations are also named "oddities" by Arnoff (1976). Among the neologisms of the wartime period, there are words formed by substitution, i.e., replacing a fragment of a known word with another, consonant fragment, while the associative connection remains tangible (Koloiz 2015: 91). For example: *putler* = *pu* + *Hitler*, *rascism* = *ra* + *fascism*, *brekhlov* = *brehlo* + *Lavrov*, *putlernet* = *putler* + *internet*. A few more neolexemes are formed by means of contamination "the combination of formally identical elements of compound words (mostly two) that have sound similarity, interpenetration of parts of the bases with their overlapping" (Koloiz 2015: 96). Examples: *putydlo* = *Putin* + *bydlo* (*bull/cattle*), *debilization* = *debil* (*moron*) + *mobilization*, *rabsiany* = *rab* (*slave*) + *Russians*, *mos'cwa* = *mos'ka* (*a little dog*) + *Moscow*, *tankeshon* = *tank* + *danke schön* (*from German: Danke schön*) – gratitude to the Germans for the tanks provided. Four abstract nouns are constructed by the method of stepwise word formation: *arestovlennia*, *orbanizatsia* (*urbanization*), *deputinizatsia* (*deputinization*), and *dekatsapizatsia* (*decapitalization*). Their peculiarity is that a new word is created from a word that is not in the usus, i.e., one link in the word formation chain is dropped (Koloiz 2015: 105). The neolexeme *arestovlennia*, like most similar nouns, is structurally derived from a verb (**arestovyty*), which does not exist, but which could be formed from the surname *Arestovych*, i.e. the neologism is formed from the surname without the presence of a middle link – a verb. Similarly, *Orban* → (**orbanize*) → *urbanization*. The words *deputinization* and *dekatsapizatsia* were formed by omitting two links each: *Putin* → (**putinizuvat*) (**putinize*) → (**putinization*) → *deputinization*; *katsap* → (**katsapize*) → (**katsapization*) → *dekatsapization*. Rederivation is the way in which a motivational word loses a morpheme, desuffixation or deprefixation occurs (Koloiz 2015: 12). The nomen *putia* is formed from the surname *Putin* by cutting off the suffix *-in-*. In total, about 11% of neologisms are formed by non-usual means.

4.2 Borrowings

The borrowings that began to be actively used during the war period include the names of foreign weapons in their original and Cyrillic spellings: *Bayraktar*, *Javelin*, *HIMARS*, *Stinger*, *Shahed*, *drone*, *Abrams*, *ATACMS*, *Patriot*, *NASAMS*, *Challenger*, *Stryker*, *Hawk*, etc. N. Klymenko calls the borrowing of lexemes in their original graphic form the medical term "transplantation" (Klymenko et al. 2008). Currently, both variants are used in parallel, and over time, perhaps, only one will remain. Most of the weapons were previously used by foreign countries, but for most Ukrainians they were unknown, so now they are perceived as neologisms. It is unusual that the names of weapons have acquired a positive connotation, the reason for this phenomenon is the possibility of using them for the good of Ukraine, for liberation from invaders, for saving lives. Some nomens entered the language

system (Burkacka 2010: 229) so quickly that they began to form their own word-formation nests, which indicates the relevance of the concepts named (Klymenko et al. 2008). For example, *stinger* → *stingerity* (*stingerite*) → *vidstingerity*, *zastingeryty*. The lexemes *bayraktar*, *javelin*, and *iskander* even passed into the category of onyms, becoming names for children born at the beginning of the full-scale invasion. Some linguists consider borrowing to be an alternative to word formation (ten Hacken 2012: 79).

4.3 Transformations

Transformations are a fairly significant group of wartime new words. In such situations, nominations of the enemy always become relevant, and negatively coloured, swear words appear, with which people seek to dehumanize, humiliate, and ridicule the enemy. After all, anger and hatred are the primary universal emotions that permeate human history and shape social narratives (Walton 2005). First of all, people's hatred is directed at dictator Putin, who ordered the war. Over the course of two years, the following newly created synonyms for his name have emerged: *putler*, *puylo*, *pukin*, *put'kin*, *putidlo*, *putyasha*, *puylusha*, *putia*, *lilliputin*, *putinochet*, *khaputin*, *kaputin*, *putloskot*, *nedofurer*, *russienfurer*, *laptenfurer*, *purer*, *hailo*, *nedomirok*, *nedopalok*, *nedoimperets*, *fsbuk*, *stsar*, *bunker commander*, and the phrase *bunker grandfather*. Nomens are formed in various ways, with the predominance of twisted, distorted versions of the surname, which is how people seek to express their anger, hatred, and at the same time contempt, humiliating the object of the nomination. A number of newly created names have a connotation of diminishment and caress (*putyasha*, *puylusha*, *putia*), which indicates the levelling of the enemy's strength and majesty, since reclamation suffixes are inappropriate when referring to the head of state. The German lexeme of the Second World War, *Führer*, which originally meant "leader" and was later used as a high officer's rank, which Hitler himself held, has been actualized. A strong associative connection with this precedent-setting historical figure is evident, and the recipient begins to subconsciously identify the objects of comparison. We can observe the active involvement of the prefix *under-* in word-formation processes; its productivity has increased over the past 30 years (Klymenko et al. 2008), it indicates an incomplete manifestation of a feature, which is also a humiliation in relation to the leader of the largest country.

A significant synonymous series of more than 30 items was formed with the name of the aggressor state: *rashka*, *rassea*, *razzia*, *srassia*, *rashia*, *rakha*, *bydlorus*, *rassiiska* *pederatsia*, *russia-federussia*, *fidirastia*, *mos'cwa*, *matskva*, *maskovia*, *maaskva*, *moskalshchyna*, *moskvabad*, *nedokraina* (*under-state*), *terrussia*, *katsapiya*, *rfa*, *rushlandia*, *rashostan*, *parashistan*, *orkostan*, *bydlostan*, *katsapstan*, *mordor*, *russian imperstan*, *aziopa*, *zadupie*. The word-formation processes involved both the modern name of the country in Ukrainian and English pronunciations and the ancient name *Moskovia*, which some of our people consider more justified because it does not single out one ethnic group in a multinational country. Russians them-

selves are against the old name because it does not reflect historical ties with Kievan Rus', of which they consider themselves the sole heirs. There is also a mockery of the Russian pronunciation of [a] in place of the unstressed o, which is one of the key phonetic differences between Ukrainian and Russian. The spelling of the double zz (*razzia*) is an allusion to the marking of Russian machinery, which reinforces the visual negative perception. The final root-*stan*, which comes from the Iranian language, translates as "land, place" and is distributed only in Asia, takes an active part in the creation of composites. There are five country names with this root: *Kazakhstan*, *Uzbekistan*, *Tajikistan*, *Pakistan*, *Afghanistan*, and three names of territorial units in the Russian Federation: *Bashkortostan*, *Tatarstan*, and *Dagestan*. Such a nomination may be a hint at the remoteness of the Russian people from European values. Such a form of government as a federation does not have a negative interpretation, but neologisms formed by contamination with a swear word have a connotation of coarseness (*pederatsia*, *fidarastia*). The nomen *russia-federussia* is formed by a rather rare non-usual method called *gendiadis*, which consists in combining two rhyming components (Koloiz 2008: 114); the new word does not carry a negative connotation, except for its humorous sound. The creation of the nomens *bydlorus*, *katsapiya*, *srasia*, *zadupie* involves swear words and rude colloquialisms, the associative connections with which are quite transparent, thus the authors seek to humiliate the object of the nomination. The purpose of creating all these synonyms was to humiliate an enemy country or to make fun of it in order to feel superior.

The Ukrainian people have replaced the name "Russians" with a group of negatively coloured synonyms: *rusnia*, *rossiantsi*, *moskalnya*, *moskalnota*, *moskovyty*, *parashentsy*, *putinoidy*, *svyno-sobaky*, *zviroidioty*, *svynorusy*, *bydlotanivtsi*, *bydlomasa*, *rusofascists*, *orc-population*, *rabsiany* (*slaves*). Collective nouns for persons (*rusnia*, *moskalnya*, *moskalnota*) have long had a tinge of disdain, so there are a limited number of such lexemes in the language, only for peoples with whom there have been serious conflicts and wars. We can also observe the consequence of humiliating the enemy to the level of animals (*svyno-sobaky*, *zviroidioty*, *svynorusy*), and the name of fantastic creatures - *orcs* - is also used. Although this is a typical example of the dehumanization of the enemy, there are sometimes calls not to use such metaphorical nominations but to call the enemy by its established name, "in order to clearly identify the perpetrators of this war" (Hrytsenko 2022: 12).

The military of the Russian army are named: *rascists*, *orcs*, *mobiks*, *chmobiks*, *chmonia*. All of them hint at a low level of mental capacity, since an intellectually developed person would not allow himself to be misled about the true purpose of being on the territory of a neighbouring state. The words *rascists* and *orcs* emphasise the anger and cruelty inherent in the prototypes of the fascists and the heroes of J. R. R. Tolkien's work. When the Russian dictator proclaimed the partial mobilisation of his people, the truncated morpheme *mob-* appeared, which, together with the suffix *-ik to*

denote a person, indicated newly mobilised soldiers, often inexperienced, confused, and poorly trained. The abbreviations with the suffixes *chmobik*, *chmonia* can be formed from the first letter of the word "partial" and 2 or 3 letters of the word "mobilisation", but associative and word-formation links with the Soviet argotism *chmo*, which has a sharply negative meaning, are clearly visible.

Synonymous names have also been given to the names of people in the Russian government known for their anti-Ukrainian stance: *brehlov*, *sad horse* (Lavrov) – the love of telling lies is emphasised, and the phrase is a metaphorical transfer based on external similarity; *pis'kov*, *moustache of the Kremlin* (Peskov) – one type of humiliation is observed in the offensive distortion of the surname and metonymic transfer based on an outstanding feature of appearance; *wid'mediv*, *alcofsb*, *narcofsb* (Medvedev) – humiliation to the level of a fantastic creature (a witch) and a hint of the person's former place of work (Federal Security Service) and his or her bad habits are observed. Supporters of the Russian dictator and his policies also attracted public attention: *bulbosaur*, *bulbofuhrer* (Lukashenko) – the first derivative is the Ukrainian dialect name for potatoes, the most famous product grown in Belarus, the root *saur-* is used only for extinct creatures and possibly hints at the venerable age of the head of state; *putlerok* (Orban) – the reclamation suffix in this case indicates distance from the original; *shmaryi* (Shariy) – a pro-Russian blogger received a nickname formed by substitution, consonant with the criminal slang name for a prostitute, apparently due to the analogy in action; *Khriak Chen Yn*, *Kon Chen Yii*, *puhliash* (Kim Jong-un) – the head of the DPRK recently attracted the attention of the Ukrainian community after it became known about his open cooperation with Putin, the nominations show a dismissive emphasis on a negative feature of appearance, we also observe a spelling neologism, the so-called neographism (Hrytsenko 2022: 10) – an unusual separate spelling of the word "Kon Chen-Yii" by analogy with the three-component anthropoformula of the Korean leader.

The Ukrainian people had a neutral attitude towards an ex US President D. Trump, no word-formation activity of the surname was observed, and only after speeches about the termination of military aid did the neologism *Trumpushka* appear – it was suffixed with the unproductive for Ukrainian language diminutive affectionate suffix *-ushk(a)*, with which only the lexeme *matushka* exists (Bevzenko 1985: 48) and can form some affectionate names in Russian. The peculiarity lies in the fact that reclamation suffixes in Ukrainian do not always bring a connotation of diminution or affection; there is an unprecedented case of adding the suffix *-enk* to the lexeme *enemy*, resulting in the nominative *vorizhenky*, which cannot be translated literally into other languages. Among emotionally coloured new words, there are also some positive ones. An example is the addition of the Ukrainian patronymic suffix *-iuk* to the surname of former British Prime Minister Boris Johnson - *Johnsoniuk*, a metaphorical "elevation" to the Cossack state, which was highly honoured. In this way,

the Ukrainian people thanked for the support and assistance in the early days of the war. In gratitude for the help, U.S. President Joe Biden was nicknamed *Baida* by one of favourite legendary Ukrainian heroes, Cossack leader, the first hetman Dmytro Vyshnevetskyi (1516-1563), who fought for the freedom of his country. The word *baida* meant “carefree person, a bachelor”, which was considered a positive characteristic, a sign of a true Cossack.

4.4 Semantic neologisms

Semantic neologisms are often formed by metaphorical transfer of a known and a new object or phenomenon by similarity. In this case, the word should have a meaning that makes the intended concept recognisable (ten Hacken 2012: 79). In times of war, weapons and ammunition became relevant, and special military vocabulary became commonly used because a larger group of people than before was involved in the use of terms and professionalisms. Semantic neologisms such as *piglets* (mortar shells), *cucumbers*, *carrots*, *zucchini* (ammunition for ATGM, LPG, RPG), and *paddle* (flamethrower) have become widespread, with metaphorical transfer based on similarity in appearance. Similarly, a new sememe of the lexeme *pixel* was formed, which now denotes the uniform of the Ukrainian military. The transfer by colour resulted in a new lexical and semantic variant of the medical professionalism *zelenka*, which now also denotes a forest belt in summer. Sound associations formed the basis for the transfer of the meaning of the lexeme *disco*, which is used to describe a battle. Due to the similarity of location in space, new meanings of the lexemes *zero* and *frontline* appeared: the line of contact with the enemy, the first line of defence. We did not find any new words formed on the basis of metonymy.

4.5 Reactivators

Reactivists traditionally constitute a small group. Only the lexeme *gauleiter* has been revived with its original meaning, as the Soviet Union during World War II called the German governors in the occupied lands, and now the Russian leaders of the temporarily occupied territories. However, in fact the German word *Gauleiter* (from Gau – district and Leiter – leader) meant the head of a district department of the National Socialist German Workers’ Party, and such titles were held by the heads of administrative-territorial units in Germany itself.

4.6 Neographemes

Neographemes appear as the author's desire to draw attention to the printed word through atypical spelling, and to stand out (Blaženović et al. 2024: 37). Zh. Koloiz calls this phenomenon graphixication, in which hyphens, brackets, quotation marks, slashes, elements of Latin graphics and other code systems can act as word-forming means: numbers, Internet signs, signs of physical and chemical formulas, etc. (Koloiz 2015: 81). In contemporary discourse, we often come across lowercase spelling of onyms, reproduction of Russian lexemes in Ukrainian graphics: *чечанепайія*, *вайска*, *персгавори*, which can be considered a manifestation of disrespect (Yarovyi 2019: 110). The letter “z” is actively used from the Latin alphabet, which, af-

ter being used to mark Russian military equipment, began to represent the commitment to aggression: *razziyskii*, *ruzznya*, *zaydy*, *zabludy*, *zviriuky* (*beasts*), *merzotnyky*, *dezertyry*, *zombi* (*zombie*). This group includes neologisms formed by lexical and syntactic means, by merging a phrase or a whole phrase into a single word that acquires a well-established meaning. For example, *yakty* (how are you?) – a manifestation of care for loved ones, *zatrydni* (*for three days*) – unrealizable plans, *analogovnet* – a much-hyped object that actually turns out to be of poor quality, *debakhnulo* – interest in danger can end tragically, *bonevtic* (*because he did not escape*) – a patriotic decision to stay with one’s country and people in difficult times.

Unfortunately, the analysed classification of neologisms is not perfect, since it allows one neologism to be included in two groups simultaneously, since it is based on the way it appears, enters the language (borrowings, new words), meaning (semantic neologisms, transformations), and nuances of spelling (neographemes).

4.7 The thematic groups of neologisms

The thematic groups of neologic vocabulary in 2022-2023 are almost exhausted by reactions to the war. After all, our social behaviour is particularly influenced by emotions and feelings (Morgado 2017: 32). The most numerous group includes negative names of the aggressor country, the second group includes swear words for the name of the head of the attacking state, the third group includes names of Russians who support the policy of their dictator, the fourth group includes names of the Russian military, the fifth group includes negatively coloured synonyms of the names of representatives of the Russian government and foreign friends of Russia, the sixth group includes names of weapons and military equipment, the seventh group includes names of military operations, and the eighth group is small, including names of patriots and defenders of Ukraine, all of which are positively coloured. The analysis confirms O. Styshov’s idea that among emotionally coloured new words, the share of lexemes with positive connotations is 10%, and with negative connotations – 90%, and also states that “speakers are generally aware of their naming activities” (Štekauer 2005).

Neologisms also differ in terms of the period of their existence; some of them become part of the active lexicon, are soon recorded in dictionaries, and remain in use, such as *rashism* and *zukuranitize*. These are mostly nomens that name a fundamentally new phenomenon, object, idea, or process that did not exist before. However, most of the new words that have appeared reactively in response to an important event of the present quickly disappear, and such words are sometimes called “ephemera” (Klymenko et al. 2008). Among the neolexemes we have studied, a significant number are one-day words. For example, in 2022 the extremely popular neologisms *chornobaity*, *macronyty*, *arrestovlennia*, etc. were used much less frequently in 2023, until they disappeared completely. A possible reason for this is the de-actualization of events and phenomena: there are no longer any battles near Chornobaivka, the President of France has expressed his position clearly, and former advisor O. Arestovych has

completely changed his rhetoric rather than issuing reassuring messages.

5. Conclusions

Thus, hate speech is unacceptable in peaceful life, but in times of war, armed confrontation, and interstate aggression, it is tolerated by the authorities. At the individual level, in stressful situations, a person may resort to hate speech to normalize their mental state. At the national level, the media sometimes use veiled forms of hostility to raise the patriotic spirit of society and unite in the face of an external enemy. Such methods proved effective at the beginning of the Russian-Ukrainian war in 2022. However, the question of the usefulness of hate speech in times of war remains unresolved due to the possible risks of increasing the level of aggression in society and the unpredictability of the consequences of nationwide aggression.

During the second year of the war, there were fewer emotional negative neologisms referring to the enemy, possibly due to the lowering of tensions in Ukrainian society. In the minds of the people, the war, which was initially a shock factor and needed to be discussed, pronounced, is moving into the category of chronically disturbing background circumstances and ceasing to be discussed in detail in online discourse. Only new extraordinary circumstances, such as North Korea's open assistance to Putin, trigger emotional reactions. The names of weapons and the most common negative synonyms for the aggressor state and its leader (*rashka*, *moskalshchyna*, *putler*) continue to be actively used, but these neologisms have lost their former sharpness in the perception of the people and have become almost neutral commonly used means of nomination. In view of this, we can predict the spread of negative vocabulary about the enemy, a slowdown in the emergence of neologisms if the war continues, and the disappearance of most of the neologisms after its end. To understand the mental state of the people during the war, it is important to study the most common current vocabulary, changes in language preferences, and the activity of neologisms.

References:

1. Arnoff, M. (1976). *Word Formation in Generative Grammar*, Mass: MIT Press, Cambridge.
2. Bahan, M., Navalna, M. & Istomina, A. (2022). Individual verbal codes of spontaneous emotional psychoregulation of modern Ukrainian youth. In *Psycholinguistics*, 31 (2), p. 6-32. [In Ukraine]. Available at: <https://psycholingjournal.com/index.php/journal/article/view/1286/352>
<https://doi.org/10.31470/2309-1797-2022-31-2-6-32>
3. Bauman, S., Perry, V. M. & Wachs, S. (2020). The rising threat of cyberhate for young people around the globe. In *Child and Adolescent Online Risk Exposure*, p. 149–175.
4. Ben-David, A. & Matamoros-Fernandez, A. (2016). Hate speech and covert discrimination on social media: Monitoring the Facebook pages of extreme-right political parties in Spain. In *International Journal of Communication*, 10, p. 1167–1193.
5. Bevzenko, S.P. (1985). *Inversion dictionary of the Ukrainian language*. Kyiv: Scientific opinion. [In

Ukraine].

6. Bhavnani, R., Findley, M. G. & Kuklinski, J. H. (2009). Rumor dynamics in ethnic violence. In *Journal of Politics*, 71, p. 876–892. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002238160909077X>
7. Blaženović, N., Hadžiahmetović Jurida S., & Muhić, E. (2024). English word formation on the internet. In *Science International journal*, 3(1), 33-41. doi: 10.35120/sciencej0301033b
8. Burkacka, I. (2010). Klasyfikacja słowotwórcza nowszych zapożyczeń. In *Linguistica Copernicana*, 2 (4), p. 229-240.
9. Castano-Pulgarín, S.A., Suarez-Betancur, N., Vega, L.M.T. & Lopez, H.M.H. (2021). Internet, social media and online hate speech. Systematic review. In *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 58, p. 1-7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2021.101608>
10. Cohen, S. J., Holt, T. J., Chermak, S. M. & Freilich, J. D. (2018). Invisible empire of hate: Gender differences in the Ku Klux Klan's online justifications for violence. In *Violence and Gender*, 5(4), p. 209-225. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1089/vio.2017.0072>
11. Dzyubina, O. I. (2018). Typological principles of classification of neologisms in modern English. In *Scientific Bulletin of the International Humanitarian University. Series: Philology*, 33(2), p. 38-40. [In Ukraine].
12. Enesi, M. (2017). The Effect of Teaching Word Formation Theory to English Students In *European Journal of Language and Literature Studies*, 7(1), p. 7-12.
13. Grlj, T. (2022) Blending as a word-formation process: a Comparative analysis of blends in english and French. In *Journal for foreign languages*, 14(1), p. 85-106.
14. Hadžiahmetović Jurida, S. (2018). Word formation in English: derivation and compounding. In *DHS-Journal for Social Sciences and Humanities, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences*, (5), p. 157-170.
15. Hadžiahmetović Jurida, S. & Rahmanović, B. (2020) Social Media Discourse: Neologisms in Various Word Formation Processes. In *Gradovrh – Journal for Literary-Linguistic, Social and Natural Science*, 16, p. 63-71.
16. Horchynska, O. Hate speech - what is it, what to do if you are its victim, how is it punished / NV. November 13, 2021. [In Ukraine]. Available at: <https://nv.ua/ukr/spec/mova-vorozhnechi-shcho-ce-shcho-roboti-yakshcho-ti-jiji-zhertva-yak-karayetsya-50195594>
17. Hrytsenko, S. (2022). Linguistic innovations of the Russian-Ukrainian war of 2022. In *Bulletin of Taras Shevchenko Kyiv National University. Literary studies. Linguistics. Folkloristics*. 2(32), p. 9-13. [In Ukraine]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17721/1728-2659.2022.32.02>
18. Isakova, T. O. (2016). Hate speech as a problem of the Ukrainian information space. In *Strategic priorities*, 4 (41), p. 90-97. [In Ukraine]. Available at: <https://ippi.org.ua/sites/default/files/isakova.pdf>
19. Jadacka, H. (1995). Częstki słowotwórcze. In *Nowy słownik poprawnej polszczyzny PWN*.

A.Markowski (red.). Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN.

20. Jadačka, H. (2001). System słowotwórczy polszczyzny (1945–2000). Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN.

21. Johnson, N. F., Leahy, R., Restrepo, N. J., Velasquez, N., Zheng, M., Manrique, P. & Wuchty, S. (2019). Hidden resilience and adaptive dynamics of the global online hate ecology. In *Nature*, 573(7773), p. 261-265. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1494-7>

22. Karpiak, O. (August 8, 2014). Cotton wool with dill: the language of political memes. In *BBC Ukraine*. [In Ukraine]. Available at: https://www.bbc.com/ukrainian/entertainment/2014/08/140807_new_words_ko

23. Klymenko, N.F., Karpilovska, E.A., & Kisylyuk, L.P. (2008). Dynamic processes in the modern Ukrainian lexicon. Kyiv: Dmytro Burago Publishing House. [In Ukraine].

24. Kokovikhina, O. (2022). Functioning of hate speech in peacetime and wartime conditions. In *Bulletin of Lviv University. Psychological sciences series*, 14, p. 15-23. [In Ukraine]. Available at: http://psysvisnyk.lnu.lviv.ua/archive/14_2022/2.pdf

25. Koloiz, Zh. V. (2015). Unusual word formation. *Kryvyi Rih: NPP Asterix*. [In Ukraine].

26. Koloiz, Zh. V. (2009). Ukrainian neology: achievements and prospects. In *Scientific works. Philology. Linguistics*, 105, p. 57-62. [In Ukraine].

27. Kotsur, V., Vilchynska, I., Nikonenko, L. & Kisse, A. (2021). The language of confrontation in everyday discourse: the intention of devaluation. In *Psycholinguistics*, 29 (1), p. 100-116. [In Ukraine]. Available at: <https://psycholing-journal.com/index.php/journal/issue/view/39/38>

28. Kovalyova, H. (2009). The opposition "one's own - another's" in the formation of national identity in the context of globalization. In *Scientific notes of the National University Ostroh Academy. Series: Philosophy*, 5, p. 84-91. [In Ukraine]. Available at: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Nznuoafs_2009_5_10

29. Ladonya, K. Yu. (2018). Neologisms in the Ukrainian language: essence, definition, principles of classification and functioning. In *Scientific Bulletin of the International Humanitarian University. Philological sciences*, 36 (1), p. 38-40. [In Ukraine]. / Available at: http://vestnik-philology.mgu.od.ua/archive/v36/part_1/12.pdf

30. Lingam, R. A. & Aripin, N. (2017). Comments on fire! Classifying flaming comments on YouTube videos in Malaysia. *Jurnal Komunikasi. In Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 33(4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17576/JKMJC-2017-3304-07>

31. Maharramova, M. (2023). Analysis of the role and use of prefixes in word formation in modern German compared to English. In *Amazonia Investiga*, 12(71), p. 233-241. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2023.71.11.20>

32. Malmqvist, K. (2015). Satire, racist humor and the power of (un)laughter: On the restrained nature of Swedish online racist discourse targeting EU-migrants begging for money. In *Discourse & Society*. Available

at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0957926515611792>

33. Meza, R., Vincze, H. O. & Mogoş, A. (2018). Targets of online hate speech in context. A comparative digital social science analysis of comments on public Facebook pages from Romania and Hungary. In *East European Journal of Society and Politics*, 4(4), p. 26-50. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17356/iee-jsp.v4i4.503>

34. Mondal, M., Silva, L., Correa, D. & Benvenuto, F. (2018). Characterizing usage of explicit hate expressions in social media. In *New Rev.Hypermedia Multimed*, 24, p. 110-130.

35. Morgado, I. (2017). *Emociones Corrosivas*. Barcelona: Ariel, Spain.

36. Ochmann, D. (2004). Nowe wyrazy złożone o podstawie zdeintegrowanej w języku polskim. *Kraków: Księgarnia Akademicka*.

37. Osovská, I. & Višňovský, J. (2023). The post-war vision in the collective cognitive space of Ukrainians and Europeans (based on contemporary mass media discourse). In *Lege artis. Language yesterday, today, tomorrow*. Trnava: University of SS Cyril and Methodius in Trnava, VIII (2), p. 15-34. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34135/lartis.23.8.2.0>

38. Ortega-Sánchez, D., Blanch, J.P., Quintana, J.I., Cal, E.S.d.l. & de la Fuente-Anuncibay, R. (2021). Hate Speech, Emotions, and Gender Identities: A Study of Social Narratives on Twitter with Trainee Teachers. In *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 18, p. 40-55. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18084055>

39. Papacharissi, Z. (2004). Democracy online: Civility, politeness, and the democratic potential of online political discussion groups. In *New Media & Society*, 6, p. 259-283. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444804041444>

40. Pryshchepa, H. (2017). "Language of hate" as a linguistic marker of "hybrid war". In *Psycholinguistics*, 22 (2), p. 98-112. [In Ukraine]. Available at: <https://psycholing-journal.com/index.php/journal/issue/view/2/22-2-2017-pdf>

41. Recomendación General nº 15, de 21 de Marzo de 2016, Sobre Líneas de Actuación en Relación con la Lucha Contra las Expresiones de Incitación al Odio; European Commission against Racism and Intolerance (ECRI): Strasbourg, France, 2016.

42. Recommendation NO. R (97) 20 of the committee of ministers to member states. Available at: <https://wcd.coe.int/com.instranet.InstraServlet?command=com.instranet>

43. Styshov, O. A. (2022). Peculiarities of word formation of complex occasionalisms in the modern Ukrainian language. In *Linguistic studies*, 43, p. 41-52. [In Ukraine].

44. Styshov, O.A. (2005). Ukrainian vocabulary of the end of the 20th century: on the material of the language of mass media. Kyiv: Pugach. [In Ukraine].

45. Štekauer, Pavol. (2005). 'Onomasiological Approach to Word-Formation'. In Štekauer, Pavol & Lieber, Rochelle (eds.). *Handbook of Word-Formation*, Dordrecht: Springer, p. 207-232.

46. Taranenko O. V. (2015). Mythological markers of enemy dehumanization in the semantic war of 2014. In *Information society*, 21, p. 65-69. [In

- Ukraine]. Available at: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/is_2015_21_13
47. ten Hacken, Pius (2012). Neoclassical word formation in english and the organization of the lexicon. In Selected papers of the 10th ICGL. Komotini/Greece: Democritus University of Thrace, p. 78-88.
48. Tretyak, M. I. Neologisms as a source of development of the Ukrainian language. [In Ukraine]. Available at: <https://conferences.vntu.edu.ua/index.php/mn/mn2019/paper/viewFile/6642/5658>
49. Walczak, B. (1992). Granica między jednostkami leksykalnymi rodzimymi i obcego pochodzenia. In Opisać słowa. Materiały ogólnopolskiej sesji naukowej w rocznicę śmierci Profesor Danuty Buttler „Teoretyczne i metodologiczne zagadnienia leksykologii”, Warszawa, pod red. A. Markowskiego.
50. Walton, S., Humanidad (2005). Una Historia de las Emociones. Mexico City: Taurus, Mexico.
51. Waszakowa, K. (2005). Przejawy internacjonalizacji w słowotwórstwie współczesnej polszczyzny. Warszawa: Wydawnictwa Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego.
52. Watanabe, H., Bouazizi, M., & Ohtsuki, T. (2018). Hate speech on twitter: A pragmatic approach to collect hateful and offensive expressions and perform hate speech detection. In IEEE Access, 6, p. 13825-13835.
53. Yarovy, D. O. (2019). Psychological practices of civil confrontation in social media. Thesis for the candidate degree in psychology. Speciality 19.00.11 - political psychology. Kyiv: Institute of Social and Political Psychology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. [In Ukraine].
54. Zasiiekina, L., Pastryk, T., Kozihora, M., Fedotova, T. & Zasiiekin, S. (2021). Cognition, Emotions, and Language in Front-Line Healthcare Workers: Clinical and Ethical Implications for Assessment Measures. Psycholinguistics, 30 (1), p. 8-25. Available at: <https://psycholing-journal.com/index.php/journal/issue/view/41/41>
55. Zhang, Z. & Luo, L. (2018). Hate speech detection: A solved problem? The challenging case of long tail on Twitter. In Semantic Web, p. 1-21. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3233/sw-180338>